

Evaluation of molecular weight and analytical assay of phenothiazine drugs

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Abstract : Methods have been developed for the molecular weight determination and analytical assay of chlorpromazine hydrochloride (CPH), diethazine hydrochloride (DH), dioxopromethazine hydrochloride (DPH) and methiomeprazine hydrochloride (MMH). The methods are based on the formation of charge-transfer complexes of the above phenothiazine derivatives with picric acid (PA). The proposed methods offer the advantages of simplicity, rapidity, sensitivity and good accuracy. The relative errors are found to be within $\pm 2.0\%$. The methods are economical compared to other costly instrumental methods of analysis.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, picric acid, phenothiazine drugs.

The present paper deals with characterisation of four phenothiazine drugs chlorpromazine hydrochloride (CPH), diethazine hydrochloride (DH), dioxopromethazine hydrochloride (DPH) and methiomeprazine hydrochloride (MMH) with respect to their molecular weight determination as well as their analytical assay. Proposed method of determination of molecular weight of the above phenothiazine drugs and their analytical assay are based on a simple charge-transfer (C-T) interaction of the drugs with picric acid. These methods have advantages of simplicity, rapidity and accuracy without the need of sophisticated chemical methods¹.

Results and discussion

Molecular weight determination :

Determination of the molecular weight of phenothiazine derivative by the spectrophotometric method is based on the C-T interaction of this compound with PA. PA has the characteristic wavelength of maximum absorption in ethanol at 360 nm with molar extinction co-efficient $15640 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. CPH, DH, DPH and MMH form 1 : 1 C-T yellow colored complexes with PA². Typical absorption spectra of PA, CPH, system in ethanol is shown in Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of these complexes showed wavelength of maximum absorption at 360 nm. This is because absorption in visible region originates from picryl component of the phenothiazine derivative in all the C-T complexes. The molecular weight of CPH-PA is calculated using the equation :

$$\epsilon = a \times M$$

where ϵ = molar extinction co-efficient of PA, a = absorptivity ($\text{L g}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), M = the molecular weight of the complex.

From this molecular weight of CPH can be calculated. Similarly, molecular weights of DH, DPH and MMH are calculated. The experimental data are average of six trials (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of PA, CPH (1) PA (8 ppm), (2) CPH-PA (16 ppm), (3) CPH (35 ppm)

Experimental

Apparatus :

A Systronics 117 spectrophotometer (Systronics, India) was used for absorbance measurements. A Sartorius-Werke (Germany) was used for all weighing purposes. Purified picric acid (PA), pure chlorpromazine

Table 1. Determination of molecular weight of phenothiazine derivatives in pharmaceutical formulation

Compd.	Beer's law limit (ppm)	Optimum range (ppm)	Molecular weight		RE (%)	RSD (%)	CV
			Calcd.	Found			
PA	0.0-33	8.0-28.0					
CPH	0.0-68.0 (CPH-PA) 0.0-40.0 (CPH)	12.0-68.0	318.86	315.84	-0.33	0.16	0.481
DH	0.0-68.0 (DH-PA) 0.0-38.0 (DH)	7.0-68.0	298.81	298.44	0.17	0.17	0.625
DPH	0.0-68.0 (DPH-PA) 0.0-39.0 (DPH)	8.0-66.0	316.68	316.42	0.36	0.24	1.028
MMH	0.0-70.0 (MMH-PA) 0.0-42.0 (MMH)	7.0-70.0	344.52	341.28	-0.82	0.48	0.325

hydrochloride, diethazine hydrochloride (May and Baker), dioxopromethazine hydrochloride (VEB, Germany) and methiomeprazine hydrochloride (Rhone poulenc) were obtained and used as received. A stock solution of 0.02 M was prepared by accurately weighing around 0.46 g of picric acid into a 100 ml standard flask. It was dissolved in double-distilled water and made up to the mark with the same. This solution was used for preparing solid phenothiazine drug and PA C-T complexes. Stock solutions of 0.5% CPH, DH, DPH and MMH were prepared with distilled water. 200 ppm solutions each of PA, CPH, DH, DPH, MMH, CPH-PA, DH-PA, DPH-PA and MMH-PA were prepared using ethanol.

Procedures :

A 10 ml of 0.02 M PA is taken in a beaker and 0.5% phenothiazine drug solution is added until there is no further precipitation. Yellow solid C-T complex of phenothiazine with PA is separated out, which is purified using distilled water and dried in vacuum desiccator over phosphorus pentoxide.

Absorption spectrum of PA is obtained by plotting absorbance versus wavelength. From the plot, wavelength of maximum absorption and molar extinction co-efficient are determined.

Determination of Beer's law limit for PA : A series of PA solutions are prepared placing different volumes (0.02-2.0 ml) of 100 ppm solution into ten different 5 ml standard flasks. Each flask is made up to the mark with ethanol. Absorbance of the solutions are measured at 360 nm against ethanol blank. Absorbance readings are plotted versus the corresponding concentrations of PA in ppm. Beer's law limit is obtained by noting the concentration of PA where the linear relationship of absorbance devi-

ates from concentration.

Determination of Beer's law limit for the phenothiazine drugs-PA C-T complexes : A series of solutions are prepared by placing different volume (0.05-3.5 ml) of 100 ppm CPH-PA C-T complex in ten separate 5 ml standard flasks. Each flask is made up to the mark with ethanol. Absorbance of each solution is measured at 360 nm against ethanol as blank. Absorbance readings are plotted versus the corresponding concentrations CPH-PA in ppm. Beer's law limit is obtained by noting the concentration of CPH-PA where the linear relationship of absorbance deviates from the concentration. Absorptivity is calculated by noting the absorbance reading at 360 nm. Similarly, Beer's law limits and absorptivity values are determined for DH-PA, DPH-PA and MMH-PA C-T complexes.

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